

Investigation into the Impact of Home Visitations on the Academic Performance of the Learners in English

Josefa Bardinias

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the home visitation and academic achievement of the learners in one of the schools in Carcar City Division as basis for an action plan. The areas of concern included the status of home visitation in terms of frequency and duration, the academic achievement of the learners, the factors that affect the academic achievement of the respondents in English as to personal, home and environment. It also determined the significant difference between the learners' academic achievement before and after home visitation and significant relationship between academic achievement and the factors that affect the academic achievement of the respondents in English. The descriptive method of research was used, employing home visitation as a strategy to improve the academic achievement of learners. The respondents were the selected learners through purposive sampling. The group was exposed to twice a week home visitation. The teacher facilitated the group with week's 1–8 self-learning modules, recorded video lessons, and televisions during implementation of the study. It revealed that before home visitation, the academic performance of the learners was Poor and there were some who had Satisfactory performance. However, after the home visitation, most of the learners had Satisfactory Performance and a minimal number of learners attained Very Satisfactory Performance. With the hope that learners at risk of failing can be addressed and learners can be provided with proper guidance in learning, the researcher envisioned to strengthen the conduct of home visitation through the implementation of strategic action plan.

Keywords: Home Visitation, Academic Achievement, Learners, Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Home visitation programs are designed to support families by fostering environments that encourage the healthy growth and development of children. These programs are tailored to meet the specific needs of families, aiming to improve child development, enhance school readiness, and foster positive interactions between parents and children (Kelley et al., 2022).

By providing personalized support in the home setting, these programs address a range of developmental and educational needs. Home visitors, who may include trained professionals such as nurses or social workers, work directly with families to offer guidance, resources, and interventions. This model allows for targeted assistance that adapts to the unique circumstances of each family (Kelley et al., 2022). The focus on individualized support helps address specific challenges faced by families and promotes effective parenting practices.

Home visitation programs can include various interventions, such as parenting education, child development activities, and health screenings. The ultimate goal is to improve outcomes for children by supporting their developmental milestones and preparing them for academic success. Evidence suggests that such programs can lead to significant benefits, including improved child behavior and academic performance. Therefore, home visitation is a versatile and impactful service delivery model that addresses multiple aspects of family and child development.

Gillespie and Dietz (2019) posited that home visitation is a multifaceted strategy that extends beyond mere observation. According to their framework, this approach involves a thorough assessment or acknowledgment of the existing learning conditions within the student's home environment. Furthermore, Gillespie and Dietz emphasize the importance of designing targeted interventions that address the specific learning challenges identified during these visits. This tailored approach aims to enhance the effectiveness of educational strategies and improve student outcomes. Overall, their perspective highlights the value of home visitations in creating a supportive and responsive educational environment.

The department of education in the Philippines was not been an exception in the process of coping the challenges during the onset of pandemic and this home visitation is also one of the delivery modes being employed by the academe to sustain the momentum of teaching – learning process and keeping the passion of the learners and teachers alive though under this unfavorable learning condition. The schools manage to employ some distant or remote learning delivery modality. Teachers were able to face this challenging scenario in order to help learners cope and pursue learning specially children with special learning needs though experiencing a difficult learning scenario (Pinatella, et al., 2021).

The researcher as a teacher for 21 years felt the need to discover some possible ways in order to alleviate performance thus this study exists with an aim to address this perennial problem in educational setting.

Along with this contention therefore, the researcher envisioned to find out how home visitation can help learners improved their academic performance under her advisory class who performed low in English subject due to habitual absences. Moreover, researcher wanted to utilize home visitation as a strategy to help learners address learning gaps due to learning loss and mis learning.

Research Questions

This study assessed the home visitation and the learners' academic achievement in English of one of the Elementary School, in Carcar City Division, Carcar City, Cebu for school year 2022-2023 as basis for action plan.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following sub – problems:

1. What is the status of home visitation and teacher's motivation in terms of;
 - 1.1 frequency; and
 - 1.2 duration?
2. What is the academic achievement of the learners before and after home visitation?
3. What are the factors that affect the academic achievement of the respondents in English as to;
 - 3.1 Personal;
 - 3.2 home; and
 - 3.3 environment?
4. Is there a significant difference between the learners' academic achievement in English subject before and after home visitation?
5. Is there a significant relationship between academic achievement and the factors that affect the academic achievement of the respondents?
6. Based on the findings, what Strategic Intervention plan can be designed?

Hypotheses

In consideration to the sub – problems the null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the learners' academic achievement before and after home visitation.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and the factors that affect the academic achievement of the respondents.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Home-visitation is a label that has been given to programs that deliver knowledge in the home. Such programs have been provided to both young and old parents, ranging in purpose, length of stay, and duration of program participation. Often the primary objective of these programs is to provide prevention or treatment. Recent attention has been given to programs that deliver in-home guidance to parents with the goal of improving educational outcomes for their child. After teacher home visits, parents were more likely to volunteer to help and be more involved at the school (Faber, 2015).

The study of Gatilogo and Tan (2019) proved that students who were considered academically at – risk have increased their academic performance after home visitation. As they revealed that there is a significant relationship between student's academic performance and their socio – demographic profile.

The belief of Bycio and Allen (2017) that interest in his studies contributes to students' academic achievement. Interest has to do with a learner's predisposition to react positively in certain ways toward a certain aspect of environment and interest is usually developed in relation to and remain allied to more basic motives. Student's interest in courses has been cited as partial explanation for overall course ratings.

The study of Wright and Shields (2018) that the foundation of the teacher home visit program rests on the school system's desire to increase student academic achievement, increase parent involvement, and motivate students to demonstrate more positive behavior in the classroom. Although there is quite a bit of time and effort involved in conducting teacher home visits, the school system felt that building parent engagement in this manner was key to the continued success of their students. In fact, building relationships between the school and the home is the driving force behind the program, furthering the system's school-home engagement and support system.

Another principle that supports in the study of Black and Waxman (2018) that majority of the students seem to have a more positive attitude and increased motivation in their daily classwork performance. Regarding teacher home visits having a positive affective impact on students' attitudes and motivation, one teacher noted, "Motivation is increased because they are more aware of communication between parent and teacher," as well as, "they [students] feel that home-school connection and trust that [the school system] is a safe and nurturing environment for them." It was added that students were dedicated and worked toward their goals more. The students knew that communication was necessary through home visits thus teachers must employ this intervention.

Home visitations involve educators visiting students' homes to engage with their families, understand students' learning environments, and provide support beyond the classroom. This approach is rooted in the belief that strong home-school connections can foster improved educational outcomes (Epstein, 2018).

Similarly, Baker and Stevenson (2015) found that home visitations that focused on literacy support helped bridge gaps between students' home and school learning environments. This bridge was especially beneficial for students from under-resourced backgrounds, as it provided additional resources and strategies for improving English language skills.

Van Voorhis and Maier (2018) conducted a study evaluating the effects of home visitations on students' literacy outcomes. Their research found that home visitations had a positive effect on reading and writing skills. The study highlighted that the personalized nature of these visits allowed educators to tailor their support to individual students' needs, which was particularly beneficial for those struggling with literacy in English.

Henderson and Mapp (2018) focused on family engagement strategies, including home visitations, and their effects on student achievement. They revealed that home visitations fostered improved home-school relationships and positively influenced students'

academic performance, including in English. The study emphasized the importance of frequent and meaningful communication between teachers and parents.

Johnson and Sanders (2019) investigated the role of home visitations in enhancing academic outcomes in a study published in *Teaching and Teacher Education*. They found that home visitations contributed to higher levels of academic achievement in English by fostering stronger partnerships between families and educators. Their findings underscored the potential of home visitations to address educational challenges and improve student success.

Gonzalez and Kim (2021) explored how home visitations impact students' academic performance, with a focus on English language learners. Their study found that structured home visitations significantly improved academic outcomes by addressing specific language barriers and providing tailored support for students and their families.

Thorough reflections and intensive scrutiny of these principles enabled the researcher to enhance and craft the action plan as the final output of the study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the descriptive – correlational research method that aims to process collected data, analyzing, interpreting and writing the results of a study (Creswell, 2002). It involves collecting data in order to test hypotheses or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study, tried to get deep data and information about the object by giving detail data and information, Gay (1992: 217). It will quantitatively tabulate the data before and after home visitation to determine any progress. It also utilizes the documentary analysis which is a popular method in a wide range of social sciences, as well as the arts. In essence, it means taking a systematic approach to understanding and interpreting documents.

The respondents of this study were 15 male and 15 female. These learners were visited twice a week. The teacher conducted the survey to find out if home visitation affected the academic achievement of the respondents.

Research Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling in the conduct of the study. Out of 39 learners enrolled, 20 learners were subjected for home visitation.

Table 1
The Research Respondents

Pupils	No. of Pupils
Boys	10
Girls	10
Total	20

As shown in the table, there are 20 respondents taken as samples from the population of 39 learners, fifteen of these learners were identified as struggling learners. The other 5 learners considered also as dependent learners. They are the ones still need the guidance of a teacher.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher primarily asked permission and approval to conduct the study in the identified school by sending a written request to the Principal then to the Schools Division Superintendent. The implementation of the study will take effect upon the notice of approval to conduct the study.

The chosen learners will be home visited for eight (8) weeks. Most of the activities were about facilitating the learning tasks found in their English Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) and answer sheets.

The selected group will be subject to the processes of home visitation. After all the important materials were prepared, the selected group underwent home visitation prior to the start of all the instructional activities. The survey result of the learners will be recorded and kept for a while. Thereafter, the group will be expose to frequent home visitation and answered answer sheets be checked and recorded to trace performance improvement.

After the exposure and with a given range of appropriate time of about eight (8) weeks, 40 item summative test questionnaires will be administered to 30 selected learners. It will administer right after all the activities and learning tasks accomplished. The result of this summative test will be included in the computation of their grades for second quarter.

After which, the researcher collected the data and subject to tallying, presentation, analysis, and interpretation. The results will be used as basis for the proposal of an action plan, which turn improved academic achievement in English.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following were the statistical measures used to analyze the data gathered by the researcher:

- Frequency and Percentage – these were used in determining the status of home visitation. These are also used in determining the academic performance of the learners in English.
- Weighted Mean for the factors that affect home visitation,
- Pearson r was used in determining the significant relationship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Status of Home Visitation

Home visitation is a service that provides within the home of families with their children in these times of pandemic. It offers support for parents to understand better their child’s development skills through learning the various competencies in English 5. Presented in Table 2 the data on home visitation.

Table 2

STATUS OF HOME VISITATION

Status	F	P
Frequency		
Once a week	3	30.0
Twice a week	5	50.0
Thrice a week	2	20.0
Duration		
Less than an hour	2	20.0
1-2 hours	1	10.
2 – 3 hours	3	30.0
3 hours or more	4	40.0

As reflected in Table 2, the status of home visitation conducted to the learners. It shows that the frequency of home visitation done was twice a week with 5 or 50.0 percent and the duration was 3 hours or more with 4 or 40.0 percent.

This means that the researcher is conducting home visitation twice a week with 3 hours or more. This activity provides opportunity for the learners to understand the competencies in English. The competencies in English are hard to understand by the learners alone. They need assistance to learn it. The teacher initiates this program to guide the learners in learning the most essential learning competencies, which are difficult for them to learn during this time of pandemic wherein the modality of learning is modular.

This implies that home visitation is evident in activity that promote help to the learners. The teacher initiated this activity to guide the learners attain mastery of the competencies. It is very important that they know the various competencies because these are essential for the pursuit of their learning in higher level.

The findings of the study are supported by Wright and Shields (2018) that the foundation of the teacher home visit program rests on the school system’s desire to increase student academic achievement, increase parent involvement, and motivate students to demonstrate more positive behavior in the classroom. Although there is quite a bit of time and effort involved in conducting teacher home visits, the school system felt that building parent engagement in this manner was key to the continued success of their students. In fact, building relationships between the school and the home is the driving force behind the program, furthering the system’s school–home engagement and support system.

Academic Achievement of Learners in English Before and After Home Visitation

Academic achievement represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environment. The academic achievement of the learners in English was measured based on their first and second quarter grades. The data on academic achievement is presented in Table 3.

Table 3

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF LEARNERS IN ENGLISH BEFORE AND AFTER HOME VISITATION

Grades	Before Home Visitation			After Home Visitation		
	f	P	Interpretation	f	P	Interpretation
90- and above	0	0	Outstanding	0	0	Outstanding
85-89	0	0	Very Satisfactory	4	13.33	Very Satisfactory
80-84	8	40.0	Satisfactory	16	86.67	Satisfactory
75-79	12	60.0	Poor	0		Poor
Below 75	0	0	Needs Improvement	0		Needs Improvement
Total	20	100		20		

Table 3 shows the academic achievement of the learners in English before and after home visitation. It reveals that before home visitation, the academic performance of learners was poor with 18 or 60.0 percent and there were some who have Satisfactory performance with 12 or 40.0 percent. On the other hand, after the home visitation there were 26 or 86.67 have Satisfactory Performance and 4 or 13.33 percent attained Very Satisfactory Performance.

This means that the learners have improved their academic performance after home visitations. Most of the learners have poor performance in before the home visitation, however they have a greater number of learners attained Satisfactory Performance after home visitation.

It implies that home visitation has improve the academic achievement of the learners. Learners are eager to learn the concept taught to them in face-to-face engagement. They interact with the teacher and ask question when they are in doubt. It is easier for them to understand the topic in English through the guidance of the teachers rather than reading the module alone.

The finding of the study is supported with the study of Black and Waxman (2018) that majority of the students seem to have a more positive attitude and increased motivation in their daily classwork performance. With regard to teacher home visits having a positive affective impact on students' attitudes and motivation, one teacher noted, "Motivation is increased because they are more aware of communication between parent and teacher," as well as, "they [students] feel that home-school connection and trust that [the school system] is a safe and nurturing environment for them." It was added that students were dedicated and worked toward their goals more. The students knew that communication was necessary through home visits, conferences, email, phone, and more. The home visit created an excellent parent-teacher relationship thus, improve the performance of the students.

Factors that Affect Academic Achievement of Learners

There are factors that affect the academic achievement in English of Grade 5 learners namely: personal, home, and environment. These factors are discussed separately.

Personal Factor. These are personal characteristics that influence the learners in the academic achievement of learners in English. The personal factors result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4

PERSONAL FACTOR

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
I play computer games more than studying.	4.30	Strongly Agree
I find it hard to understand English subject.	4.20	Agree
I like to study.	4.00	Agree
I find English boring to learn.	3.20	Neutral
English is my favorite subject.	2.53	Disagree
Grand Weighted Mean	3.65	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree, 1.81-2.60 – Disagree, 2.61-3.40 – Neutral, 3.41-4.20 – Agree, 4.21-5.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 4 presents the personal factors that affect the academic achievement of the learners . It shows that the respondents Strongly Agree with 4.30 weighted mean on the indicator "I play computer games more than studying" which is considered as the highest indicator however, the lowest indicator reveals that "English is my favorite subject" with the weighted mean of 2.53 with the verbal interpretation of Disagree.

This means that the learners considered playing computer games as personal factor in the academic achievement. It is very rampant to the learner that they engaged in online computer games. Most of the time was in the computer because they felt happy when they are doing it. On the other hand, they did not consider English as their favorite subject that is why they don't take the subject seriously. They find the subject difficult especially during this pandemic wherein they are learning in their own pace.

It implies that computer games hinder the learners' academic achievement in English in this pandemic. They tend to use most of their times in engaging with the online games. It is very important that parents should provide guidance to their children to minimize the use of computer for leisure. Using computer is beneficial if the learners used it for educational purposes. Thus, direct supervision of the parents is needed to achieve academic success in English. Their interest in learning English is not an evident because they find the subject difficult.

The result of the study is supported with Bycio and Allen (2017) that interest in his studies contributes to students' academic achievement. Interest has to do with a learner's predisposition to react positively in certain ways toward a certain aspect of environment and interest is usually developed in relation to and remain allied to more basic motives. Student's interest in courses has been cited as partial explanation for overall course ratings.

Home Related Factors. These are certain essential influence of the learners in achieving academic success at home. The factors are discussed in Table 5.

Table 5

HOME RELATED FACTORS

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
I have a lot of household chores to do.	4.50	Strongly Agree
My family do not speak English.	4.43	Strongly Agree
I am task to baby sit my younger brother or sister so I cannot study.	4.27	Strongly Agree
My family does not like me to use English in our home.	4.23	Strongly Agree
My siblings bully me when I speak English.	4.10	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	4.31	Strongly Agree

Legend:

1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree, 1.81-2.60 – Disagree, 2.61-3.40 – Neutral, 3.41-4.20 – Agree, 4.21-5.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 5 shows the home related factors that affect the academic achievement of the learners . It reveals that the home related factors that affect the academic achievement was the indicator, "I have a lot of household chores to do" with the weighted mean of 4.50 or Strongly Agree, however the least indicator was "My siblings bully me when I speak English" with 4.10 or Agree.

This means that the home related factor that affect academic achievement in English was the household chores which are too many. The learners perform most of the chores at home because their parents are working and doing business to sustain their daily living. It implies that household chores affect the academic achievement of the learners in English. The learners cannot concentrate in working on his printed module because parents assigned to many tasks at home. The learners have insufficient time in studying their printed module which resulted to poor academic achievement.

The finding is supported with the study of Yusuf (2011) that home environment is a predictor of academic achievement. The family has an important role to play in the education of children. Thus, parent's support is essential in attaining academic achievement of the child.

Environmental Factors. These are external factors that affect to the individual and can have a positive or negative influence on a person's participation and academic achievement. The result of environmental factors are presented in Table 6.

Table 6

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
I like to play outside with my neighbors than studying.	4.34	Strongly Agree
I watch television in my neighbor's house so I don't have time to study.	2.93	Neutral
I cannot study well because of the noise made.	2.57	Disagree
Our neighborhood always plays with karaoke.	2.53	Disagree
I usually go with my "barkada" especially when they roam around the city.	2.37	Disagree
Grand Weighted Mean	2.95	Neutral

Legend:

1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree, 1.81-2.60 – Disagree, 2.61-3.40 – Neutral, 3.41-4.20 – Agree, 4.21-5.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 6 reflects the environmental factors that affect the academic achievement of the learners. It reveals that the environmental factors that affect the academic achievement was the indicator, "I like to play outside with my neighbors than studying" with 4.34 or Strongly Agree, however the least indicator was, "I usually go with my "barkada" especially when they roam around the city", with 2.37 or Disagree.

This means the learners considered the neighbor playmates as an environmental factor in academic achievement. The learners easily tempted with their neighbor in playing rather than studying. Children at their age always have fun in playing with their peers. They don't take studying seriously.

It implies that peer influence affects the academic achievement of the learners. Parental guidance is necessary for the learners to achieve academic success. It is the role of the parents to support their child's education.

The finding of the study is parallel with Opore (2012) that peer group relationship lead to acts of truancy and absenteeism on the part of the students. Adolescence is a period of increasing influence of one's peers and peer values and a diminished role of parents as primary reference group.

Summary of the Factors that affect Academic Achievement in English 5

These are the summary of the factors that affect the academic performance of the learners. These are personal, home related, and environmental factors. The result is presented in Table 7.

Table 7

SUMMARY OF THE FACTOR THAT AFFECT ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Home Factor	4.31	Strongly Agree
Personal Factor	3.65	Agree
Environmental Factor	2.95	Neutral
Grand Weighted Mean	3.64	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree, 1.81-2.60 – Disagree, 2.61-3.40 – Neutral, 3.41-4.20 – Agree, 4.21-5.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 7 shows the summary of the factors that affect academic achievement of the learners. It is reflected in the table that among the aforementioned factors, the highest was home factors with 4.31 or Strongly Agree and the lowest was environmental factor with 2.95 or neutral.

This means that respondents perceived that home related factors affect the academic achievement of the learners. The learners have too many household chores at home. They were not able to study and perform their task in the printed module because of their household chores.

It implies that parents should create a mechanism that lessen the household chores of their children. Their support to their study is essential for them to attain success in English.

The result is supported with the study of Kingdom (2016) that home factors have significant correlation with student's academic achievement. The family economic status as being significantly related to academic success. The low caste learners have significantly lower achievement than their non-low caste colleagues, even after controlling for parental education and household wealth.

Significant Difference between the Academic Achievement of the Learners Before and After Home Visitation

The academic achievement of the learners before and after home visitation were compared to find out the significant mean gain at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 8.

Table 8

DIFFERENCE IN ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT BEFORE AND AFTER HOME VISITATION

Tests	Mean	Sd	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Before Home Visitation	79.2	1.65	0.00	Reject H ₀	Significant
After Home Visitation	83.37	1.16			

As reflected in Table 7, the significant difference in the academic achievement of the learners before and after home visitation in Liburon Elementary School. It was found out that the p-value of 0.00 is lesser than the level of significance of 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the academic achievement in English before and after home visitation. The academic achievement of the learners improved significantly after home visitation. It is evident in the mean before home visitation which is 79.2 or poor performance and became 83.37 which is Satisfactory Performance.

It implies that home visitation is effective in improving the academic achievement of the learners in English. Learners' academic performance increases significantly because they are guided by the teacher in doing various activities in the module. Home visitation creates a positive impact to the academic achievement of the learners. Students are motivated to learn through the guidance of the teachers.

The result of the study affirms the study of Wright and Shield (2019) that around one-third of the teachers reported that teacher home visits had a positive academic impact on students due to behaviors shown in class, such as increased focus or motivation. The teachers surveyed reported that they noticed a positive affective impact on student academic achievement after completing teacher home visits, which many respondents attributed to the cultivation of important relationships with both students and their parents. Slightly over four percent of teachers responded that there was a slight or temporary positive impact on student achievement after teacher home visits but did not see the changes as significant or long lasting.

Significant Relationship between the Academic Achievement and Factors that Affect the Academic Achievement

The variables are tested at 0.05 level of significance to find out if there are significant relationship between academic achievement and factors that affect the academic achievement. The result is presented in Table 9.

Table 9

SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND FACTORS THAT AFFECT THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Variables	Academic Achievement		Decision	Interpretation
	r-value	p-value		
Personal	0.73	0.01	Reject H ₀	Significant
Home	0.89	0.00	Reject H ₀	Significant
Environment	0.78	0.00	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 9 shows the significant relationship between the academic performance and factors that affect the academic achievement of the learners in English. It reveals that personal, home, and environment have p-value which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, therefore reject the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant relationship between personal, home, and environmental factors and academic achievement of Grade 5 learners. It further signifies that the r-values of personal which is 0.73, home which is 0.89, and environment which is 0.78 which means that they have strong positive relationship.

It implies that personal, home, and environment are associated with academic performance. They are predictors of academic achievement of learners in English.

The result affirms the study of Gatilogo and Tan (2019) students who were considered academically at-risk have increased their academic performance after home visitation. There is a significant relationship between students' academic performance and their socio-demographic profile such as age and parents' education and employment status, and number of siblings. Teaching style as personal model has also a significant relationship to the academic performance of the students and the contact information/activity invitation of teachers. This is further supported with "The Parents as Teachers Program" (Parents as Teachers National Center, 2008), that through home visits, schools can help establish positive relationships with families, leading to more involvement in schools and better student success.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that home visitation has improved the academic achievement of the learners. The factors that affect their academic performance were personal, home, and environment. They are significantly related to academic achievement of the learners. This proves the theory of Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory approach that underlines the importance of the family and neighborhood interacting with the physical environment. That, home visiting programs are based on ecological theory, which postulates that the child develops in a multi-faceted environment (Bronfenbrenner,1992). It focuses on the quality and context of the child's environment. It further proves that, home visitation of teachers allows to build fundamental relationships with their learner's and create a more trustworthy and comfortable learning environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher endorsed that

1. the teacher may strengthen home visitation program;
2. the school may provide support, like transportation allowance, to the teachers who are part of the home visitation program;
3. teacher shall conduct an intensive parenting seminar to the parents of academically at-risk learners.
4. the school may provide instructional materials for teachers conducting home visitation;
5. Parents shall demonstrate positive support in the home visitation program; and
6. Parallel studies may be conducted with the suggested titles:
 - a. Home Visitation Program in Mathematics and Science;
 - b. Parental Support in Home Visitation Program; and
 - c. A Sustainable Home Visitation Program towards Learners Progress in Core Subject Areas.

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